

Malleolar Fractures: Surgical Site Infection and its Risk Factors

Author: Dr Justin Thomas

Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics,
Government Medical College Thiruvananthapuram,
Kerala, India.

Guide: Dr Ramanujam. P.

1Additional Professor, Department of Orthopaedics,
Government Medical College Thiruvananthapuram,
Kerala, India

Abstract:-

INTRODUCTION : Post operative infection is a dreadful complication of orthopaedic surgery. Implant associated infection can lead to a spectrum of complications from non union to sepsis and even amputation. Infection leads to increased duration of hospital stay and increased chance of nosocomial infections which adds morbidity of patient. Thus to identify the risk factors of implant associated infection and to reduce or avoid those prior to, as well as during surgery.

OBJECTIVES: To estimate risk factors that are associated with surgical site infection following malleolar fracture surgeries.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: This case: control research was conducted at the Government Medical College in Thiruvananthapuram from January 2021 to December 2021. For this investigation, 40 cases and 40 controls were collected.

RESULTS: 11 factors were examined for any correlation with the likelihood of implant-related infection. We discovered a significant correlation between the risk of infection and diabetes with no glycemic control (chi square 7.02 and p 0.007), smoking (chi square 11.3 and p 0.0007), open fracture (chi square 8.49 and p 0.004), the presence of blebs (chi square 11 and p 0.009), and the length of surgery (chi square 8.49 and p 0.003).

CONCLUSIONS: In the study of risk factors of surgical site infection we found diabetes mellitus, smoking, open fractures, and duration of surgery and blebs had a significant association. Pre op control of glycemic levels, strict smoking cessation and correction of skin status before surgery may reduce surgical site infection.

Keywords:- Implant associated infection, orthopaedic infection, orthopaedic surgical site infections, biofilm.

I. INTRODUCTION

An ankle "fracture" is another term for a broken ankle. This indicates that one or more of the ankle joint's bones are shattered. A broken ankle can range from a straightforward break in one bone, which might not prevent you from walking, to several fractures, which may need you to avoid putting weight on it for several months and force your ankle out of place. Simply, the ankle gets more unstable the more bones are shattered in it. Additionally, ligaments could be harmed. Ankle ligaments stabilise the joint and bones of the ankle.

Ankle fractures include two joints, where the tibia, fibula, and talus connect is the ankle joint. The ligaments that hold the tibia and fibula together at the syndesmosis joint. Many ligaments contribute to the stability of the ankle joint.

Pain, bruising, swelling, and the inability to bear weight on the affected limb are possible symptoms. An associated high ankle sprain, compartment syndrome, a reduction in range of motion, and malunion are possible complications.

The stability of the ankle joint determines how to treat fractures of the ankle.

When a fracture pattern is considered stable, it can be treated similarly to a sprained ankle. All other forms call for surgery, most frequently an open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF), which is done using permanently implanted metal hardware to hold the bones in place while the body heals itself.

After surgery, the ankle will need to be immobilised with a cast or splint.

Children with generally stable fractures may recover more quickly with an ankle brace as opposed to a full cast. The majority of individuals with a malleolus fracture need to be immobilised for 6 weeks. Patients who underwent surgical treatment or those with an initially non-displaced fracture will often need to be immobile for 4 weeks.

A. Biofilm

A structured colony of bacterial cells encased in a self-produced polymeric matrix that is adhered to an inert or living surface is what William Costerton refers to as a biofilm. The development of biofilms is a coordinated process among several bacterial cells, even between different bacterial species, on occasion. Sometimes the initial biofilm-forming organisms provide the right environment for the recruitment of new species. Biofilm is made up of hydrophilic, sparingly soluble biopolymers, also known as extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) or biofilm. The most prevalent polymerized-N-acetylglucosamine (PNAG) biofilm EPS in *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis* is. The three stages of biofilm formation— attachment, maturity, and dissemination.

II. TREATMENT

A. Acute Infection:

A severe infection It should be highlighted that early, acute infection following an open fracture or internal fixation is typically brought on by a virulent organism, causing rapid tissue death, bone loss, fixation failure, and consequent non-union. For the fixation to be saved and these consequences to be avoided, immediate treatment is required. Antibiotics alone cannot be relied upon for nonoperative therapy. It is generally acknowledged that fractures can heal when there is an infection. As long as they are stable, have healthy soft tissue coverage, and have efficient antibacterial suppression. Early-presenting infected fractures should undergo surgical examination of the site and deep sample collection. All dead tissue, including bone fragments that are not viable, should be removed, and abscesses should be drained. There should be no effort made to maintain large dead bone fragments to preserve stability, as this will maintain bacterial biofilm and lead to an infected nonunion. After resection broad-spectrum intravenous antibiotics should be given, which will cover the range of causative organisms.

B. Chronic infection

One of the two ways chronic infection typically manifests itself is late. The infection can progress and finally present with a much more complex appearance if an early infection is overlooked or treated ineffectively with antibiotic. Typically, this will appear as delayed presentation between 10-12 weeks of the incident and fracture that has not healed. Low virulence organisms, on the other hand, can produce subclinical infection without showing any early clinical indications.

In such a case, the patient will typically come with localized edema or indolent pain rather than fistula or widespread illness.

➤ Late presentation

After several months of infection, the fracture will either heal or continue to be infected. Without treatment, it is unlikely to develop to healing. Both urgency and treatment are absent. Correct any general medical issues in these patients before surgery, quitting smoking, enhancing diet, paying attention to diabetic management, and enhancing vascular status. To increase the yield after surgery, antimicrobial therapy should be terminated after the patient is feeling better overall at least two weeks beforehand.

C. Late presentation with healed fracture

After the bone has healed after a fracture, an infection could develop. Prior to discharge from the fracture or surgical scars, patients frequently experience pain, edema, and other generalised symptoms. The principles of managing chronic osteomyelitis are used in the course of treatment. Deep samples for histology and microbiological should be collected once the implant is removed.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Risk factors associated with surgical site infection following malleolar fracture fixation

A. STEPS IN DATA COLLECTION

- Diagnosis is confirmed in post operative malleolar fracture fixation patients
- 2. Radiograph of ankle obtained
- IP register
- Operative notes
- Interview the patient
- Culture report of microbiology dept

B. VARIABLES

Age, Gender, level of physical activity, physical demands, Compliance to doctors orders.

IV. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The study group consisted of patients who underwent malleolus fracture fixation surgery in the IP division of the Orthopaedics department and were either diagnosed with (cases) operative site infection or were not. Prior to including patients in the sample group, their consent was obtained, and those who refused to take part in the study were omitted as well.

Risk factors assessed are:

- **Age:** patients of all age group are included in the study. They are divided into various groups <20yrs, 20-40yr, 49-65yrs, >65yrs.
- **Gender:** Samples are grouped into male and female.
- **Nature of fracture:** Fractures are classified to open or closed based on Gustillo Anderson classification system
- **Diabetes:** Samples are grouped into
 - ✓ No disease
 - ✓ Controlled diabetes on OHA
 - ✓ Controlled diabetes on insulin
 - ✓ Uncontrolled diabetes
- **Smoking:** samples are grouped into smokers and non smokers.
- **BMI:** Grouped into 4
 - ✓ <18.5 - underweight
 - 2. 18.5- 24.9 - normal
 - ✓ 25- 29.9 - overweight
 - ✓ >30- obesity
- **Blebs:** samples are grouped into presence of blebs or not before surgery
- **Timing of surgery:** samples are grouped based on time gap between trauma and patients surgery time
 - ✓ Surgery done within 12hrs of injury
 - ✓ Surgery done after 12hrs of injury
 - ✓ Surgery done after 2 weeks after injury
 - ✓ Nature of fracture:

Samples are grouped based on whether it is an open fracture or closed fracture.

- **Duration of surgery:** samples are grouped based on duration taken for surgery.
 - ✓ Less than 90mins
 - ✓ More than 90mins

- Fracture pattern : Radiographs of ankle of the samples are grouped based on Danis Weber pattern of injury of ankle fracture.
 - ✓ Danis Weber type A
 - ✓ Danis Weber type B
 - ✓ Danis Weber type C
- **Microbiological Profile:** samples are grouped according to organism cultured from the pus from the wound site.

V. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

We studied 40 cases with surgical site infection following malleolus fracture operative fixation and 40 controls with no infection following malleolus fracture operative fixation . The following are the observations made and available data is analysed as follows:

A. Age Distribution

Table 1: Age distribution

Age	Cases		Controls	
<20 years	0	0%	0	0%
20-40 years	4	10%	2	5%
40-60 years	15	37.5%	24	60%
>60 years	21	52.5%	14	35%

- The range of Age in the control group is from 29 to 74years .
- The range of Age in the case group is from 31 to 79 years.
- Mean Age in the case group is 58years .
- Mean Age in the case group is 52 years.

Age distribution case group

Fig. 3: Age distribution in case group

Age distribution control group

Fig. 4: Age distribution in control group

B. GENDER DISTRIBUTION

Table 2: Gender distribution

Gender	Cases		Controls		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Male	19	47.5	27	67.5	46	57.5
Female	21	52.5	13	32.5	34	42.5
Total	40				80	

- In the case group 47.5% comprises of males and 52.5% comprises of females.
- In the control group 67.5% comprises of males and 32.5% comprises of females.
- Out of Total 80 subjects 57.5% are males and 42.5% are females

Gender distribution among whole study

Fig. 5: GENDER distribution of whole study

meta-chart.com

Fig. 6: GENDER distribution among case and control

C. TIMING OF SURGERY

Table 3: Timing of surgery

Timing	Cases		Controls		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
<12hrs	6	15	10	25	16	20
>12hrs	14	35	9	22.5	23	28.75
Delayed	20	50%	21	52.5	41	51.25

Fig. 7: Timing of surgery among case and controls

Fig. 8: Timing of surgery

- 50% of the cases surgery is done after 2 weeks after the skin condition improves, edema subsides and blebs subsides

- 10 patients that is 25% of subjects in the control group had their surgeries done within 12 hrs of trauma.

D. BODY MASS INDEX

Table 4: BMI

BMI	Case		Control		Total	
Underweight	13	32.5%	14	35%	27	33.75%
Normal	11	27.5%	13	32.5%	24	30%
Overweight	12	30%	10	25%	22	27.5%
Obese	4	10%	3	7.5%	7	8.75%

Body mass index among Total subjects (N =80)

■ UNDERWEIGHT ■ NORMAL ■ OVERWEIGHT ■ OBESE

Fig. 9: BMI among total subjects

Fig. 10: BMI among Cases and controls

- 16 patients , that is 40% of the patients in case group have their BMI as overweight or obese.

E. DURATION OF SURGERY

Table 5: Duration of surgery

Duration of surgery	Cases		Controls		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
<90 mins	12	30	25	62.5	37	46.25
>90 mins	28	70	15	37.5	43	53.75
Total	40		40		80	

- Mean Duration of surgery in case group is 83 minutes.
- Mean Duration of surgery in control group is 129 minutes.

Fig. 11: Duration of surgery among subjects

Fig. 12: scatter plot of Duration of surgery among cases

F. DIABETES MELLITUS (DM)

Table 6: diabetes mellitus

Groups	Case		Control		Total	
NO DIABETES	8	20%	10	25%	18	22.5%
DM ON OHA GOOD CONTROL	10	25%	11	27.5%	21	26.25%
DM ON INSULIN GOOD CONTROL	4	10%	12	30%	16	20%
NO GLYCEMIC CONTROL	18	45%	7	17.5%	25	31.25%

Diabetes Mellitus group among cases (n=40)

■ No DIABETES ■ DIABETICS ON OHA CONTROL
■ DIABETICS ON INSULIN CONTROL ■ NO GLYCEMIC CONTROL

Fig. 13: DM group among cases

Diabetes Mellitus group among controls (n=40)

Fig. 14: DM group among controls

Diabetes Mellitus

Fig. 15: DM and infection

Patients with good glycemic control with oral hypoglycemics or insulin tend to have less chance of infection when directly compared to the case group.

G. DANIS WEBER TYPE OF FRACTURE PATTERN

Table 7: fracture pattern

	Cases		Controls		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
TYPE A	5	12.5	9	22.5	14	17.5
TYPE B	10	25	11	27.5	21	26.25
TYPE C	25	62.5	20	50	45	56.25

Danis Weber fracture pattern type(percentage)

Fig 16: DANIS WEBER TYPE OF FRACTURE PATTERN AMONG CASE AND CONTROLS (PERCENTAGE)

Fig. 17: Danis Weber type of fracture pattern among cases

- 45 out of 80 subjects had sustained Danis Weber type C fracture pattern which is infrasyn desmotic.

H. SMOKING

Table 8: Smoking among case and controls

SMOKING	Cases		Controls		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
YES	26	65	11	27.5	37	46.25
NO	14	35	29	72.5	43	53.75
Total	40		40		80	

Fig. 18 smoking and infection

I. PRESENCE OF BLEBS

Table 9: Presence of blebs

BLEBS	Cases		Controls		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
YES	22	55	12	30	34	42.5
NO	18	45	28	70	46	57.5
Total	40		40		80	

BLEBS AND RISK OF INFECTION(N=80)

Fig. 19: Blebs and Risk of Infection (N=80)

J. MICROORGANISMS

Table 10: microorganisms isolated

Microbiological organism	N	%
STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS	17	42.5%
PSEUDOMONAS	7	17.5%
KLEBSIELLA	5	12.5%
PROTEUS MIRABILIS	4	10%
STERILE FOR AEROBIC AND ANAEROBIC	7	17.5%

Microbiology among case group(%)

Fig: 20: Micro Organisms

- Most common organism isolated from wound infection is Staphylococcus aureus bacteria.
- Pseudomonas, PROTEUS MIRABILIS, Klebsiella also isolated In significant numbers.

K. FRACTURE (OPEN / CLOSED)

Table 11: Fracture open or closed

Type of fracture	Cases		Controls		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Closed	12	30	25	62.5	37	46.25
Open	28	70	15	37.5	43	53.75
Total	40		40		80	

OPEN FRACTURES (Based on Gustillo Anderson classification)

Fig. 21: OPEN FRACTURE AND INFECTION

- The fracture type is classified based on Gustillo - Anderson classification.

VI. INFERENCE ANALYSIS

A. Timing of surgery

Table 12: Surgery done in less than 12 hrs from trauma

				Chi square	df	p
Surgery done in less than 12 hours		Cases	Controls	1.25	1	0.26
	+	6	10			
	-	34	30			

• There is a decreased risk of infection in subjects with surgery done within 12 hours of injury. There is negative association between presence of Infection and surgery done

in less than 12 hours of trauma (Odds ratio : 0.52) .There is no evidence of level of statistical significance (p value >0.26).

Table 13: Surgery done in more than 12 hrs from trauma

				Chi square	df	p
Surgery done in more than 12 hours		Cases	Controls	1.52	1	0.21
	+	14	9			
	-	26	31			

• Presence of Infection in subjects is more when surgery done after 12 hours of trauma. There is a slight positive

association (Odds ratio = 1.47) . There is no evidence of level of statistical significance (p value =0.21).

Table 14: Surgery done delayed

				Chi square	df	p
Surgery done delayed after 2 weeks		Cases	Control	0.05	1	0.82
	+	20	21			
	-	20	19			

• Presence of Infection in case group is more in the delayed surgery. There is a slight positive association (Odds ratio =

1.1) . There is no evidence of level of statistical significance (p value >0.82).

B. BODY MASS INDEX

Table 15: UNDERWEIGHT SUBJECTS

				Chi square	df	p
BMI UNDERWEIGHT		Cases	Controls	0.05	1	0.81
	+	13	14			
	-	27	26			

Table 16: NORMAL SUBJECTS

				Chi square	df	p
Normal BMI		Cases	Controls	0.23	1	0.62
	+	11	13			
	-	29	27			

Table 17: OVERWEIGHT SUBJECTS

				Chi square	df	p
BMI OVERWEIGHT		Cases	Controls	0.25	1	0.61
	+	12	10			
	-	28	30			

Table 18: OBESE SUBJECTS

				Chi square	df	p
BMI OBESE		Cases	Controls	0.15	1	0.69
	+	4	3			
	-	36	37			

- There is a negative association between infection and BMI when subject is Underweight or normal. (Odds ratio <1).However there is no evidence of statistical significance (p value = 0.8 and 0.6 respectively / > 0.05).

- There is a positive association between infection and BMI when the subject is overweight or Obese (Odds ratio = 1.28 and 1.37 respectively). However there is no evidence of statistical significance (p value = 0.6 / > 0.05).

C. DURATION OF SURGERY

Table 19: Duration of surgery less than 90 minutes

		Cases	Controls	Chi square	df	p
Surgery duration less than 90 minutes				8.49	1	0.003
	+	12	25			
	-	28	15			

Table 20: Duration of surgery more than 90 minutes

		Cases	Controls	Chi square	df	p
Surgery done in more than				8.49	1	0.003
	+	28	15			
	-	12	25			

- There is a positive association between risk of infection and Duration of surgery more than 90 minutes. (Odds Ratio 3.88). There is significant level of statistical significance (p value less than 0.05).

- There is a negative association between risk of infection and Duration of surgery less than 90 minutes. (Odds Ratio 0.25). There is significant level of statistical significance(p value less than 0.05).

D. DIABETES MELLITUS

Table 21: SUBJECTS WITH NO DIABETES

		Cases	Controls	Chi square	df	p
No Diabetes				0.069	1	0.79
	+	8	10			
	-	32	30			

Table 22: SUBJECTS WITH DIABETES ON OHA

		Cases	Controls	Chi square	df	p
DIABETICS ON OHA				0.064	1	0.79
	+	10	11			
	-	30	29			

Table 23: SUBJECTS WITH DIABETES ON INSULIN

		Cases	Controls	Chi square	df	p
DIABETICS ON INSULIN				0.58	1	0.44
	+	4	12			
	-	36	28			

Table 24: SUBJECTS WITH DIABETES WITH NO GLYCEMIC CONTROL

		Cases	Controls	Chi square	df	p
Diabetics with no glycerin control				7.04	1	0.007
	+	18	7			
	-	22	33			

- There is negative association between risk of infection among no diabetes group , Diabetics on good glyceimic control with OHA, Diabetics on good glyceimic control with insulin (Odds ratio <1 in all groups).There was no evidence of statistical significance in these groups (p value more

- than 0.05).
- There is positive association between risk of infection and subjects with no glyceimic control .
- (Odds ratio : 2.02) . There is significant level of significance as p value is less than 0.05.

E. DANIS WEBER TYPE OF FRACTURE PATTERN

Table 25: fracture pattern DW type A

				Chi square	df	p
DANIS WEBER TYPE A		Cases	Controls	1.38	1	0.23
	+	5	9			
	-	35	31			

Table 26: fracture pattern DW type B

				Chi square	df	p
DANIS WEBER TYPE B		Cases	Controls	0.064	1	0.79
	+	10	11			
	-	30	29			

Table 27: fracture pattern DW type C

				Chi square	df	p
DANIS WEBER TYPE C		Cases	Controls	1.26	1	0.26
	+	25	20			
	-	15	20			

• There is negative association between risk of infection and Danis Weber type A and type B fracture pattern (Odds ratio <1). However there is no level of statistical significance (p value >0.05).

• There is positive association between risk of infection and Danis Weber type C fracture pattern (Odds ratio >1). However there is no level of statistical significance (p value >0.05).

F. SMOKING

Table 28: Smoking

				Chi square		
SMOKING		Cases	Controls	11.3	1	0.0007
	+	26	11			
	-	14	29			

• There is positive association between risk of infection and Smoking (Odds ratio >1). However there is evidence of level of statistical significance (p value <0.05).

• There is negative association between risk of infection and subjects with no smoking (Odds ratio <1). However there is significant level of statistical significance (p value <0.05).

G. Presence of blebs

Table 29: Presence of blebs

				Chi square		
PRESENCE OF BLEBS		Cases	Controls	5.11	1	<0.05
	+	22	12			
	-	18	28			

• There is positive association between risk of infection and presence of blebs (odds ratio >1). However there is evidence of level of statistical significance (p value <0.05).

• There is negative association between risk of infection and presence of blebs (Odds ratio <1). However there is significant level of statistical significance (p value <0.05).

H. MICROBIOLOGY

Table 30: Micro Organisms Isolated

Microbiological organism		
STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS	17	42.5%
PSEUDOMONAS	7	17.5%
ACINETOBACTER	5	12.5%
PROTEUS MIRABILIS	4	10%
STERILE FOR AEROBIC AND ANAEROBIC	7	17.5%

I. FRACTURE (OPEN / CLOSED)

Table 31: Open Fractures

			Chi square	df	p value
OPEN FRACTURES	Cases	Controls	8.49	1	<0.05
	+	28	15		
	-	12	25		

- There is positive association between risk of infection and presence of open fractures (odds ratio >1). However there is evidence of level of statistical significance (p value <0.05).
- There is negative association between risk of infection and presence of blebs (Odds ratio <1). However there is significant level of statistical significance (p value <0.05)

VII. DISCUSSION

In our study, the average case age was 58 years old, compared to 52 years for control. Age and risk of surgical site infection following an ankle fracture were not significantly correlated.

Mohamed Al-Mayahi et al. and Muhammad Thahir et al found no correlation between age and risk of implant-associated infection in similar investigations.

Age-related risk was discovered by Dr. Amaradeep G. et al. in their 2013 study. In our investigation, no gender-related risk of significance was discovered. Mohamed Al-Mayahi et al. study produced similar findings.

Similar research was conducted in Ghana by Stephen Apanga et al.14 and revealed greater risk in males. 30 controls (75%) and 32 cases (80%) both had diabetes mellitus. Among cases, there were 25% and 10% of diabetics with good glycemic control with OHA or insulin, compared to 27.5 and 30% among controls.

It was discovered that the prevalence of diabetes in the controls was similar to the group with diabetes today. Perioperative hyperglycemia following total joint arthroplasty, according to Zmistowski et al., is a risk factor for infection.

Four cases (10%), three controls (7.5%), and twelve patients (30%) were overweight. Obesity and the risk of implant-related infection have not been shown to be significantly correlated. Michelle M. Dowsey and Malinzak conducted related research and discovered that whereas obesity alone does not raise the incidence of implant-associated infection, morbid obesity (BMI > 40) does.

Smoking was found to have a substantial connection with the risk of ankle fracture in our study (Chi square 8.49, p = 0.004). Compound fractures are more likely than closed fractures to get infected. The outcomes are comparable to those of the pioneers in this field, Gustilo-Anderson et al. We also saw that the risk of infection rose as we descended the

Gustilo and Anderson types. There were open and closed fractures in the sample. Internal implants are much less contaminated than fractures treated with exterior fixative devices (chi square value 4.809 and p value 0.028). Because more compound fractures require more external fixations to stabilize them than less compound ones, this demonstrates a certain false link. Of course, the likelihood of infection is higher with more compound fractures. This information was previously discussed and supported by a study done by Gustilo-Anderson.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In the present study of risk factors for infection associated with operative fixation of malleolus fracture we have studied 11 variables for any significant association with risk of surgical site infection. We found diabetes mellitus patients with no glycemic control, smokers, open fractures, duration of surgery more than 90 minutes, presence of blebs have significant level of association with infection. Future studies are recommended for validation of the observed risk factors.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Strict glycemic control before and after the surgery may reduce the risk of surgical site infection.
- Smoking cessation helps in skin vascularity and reduce the risk of infection.
- Duration of surgery should be less than 90 minutes if possible may reduce the risk of infection.
- Give adequate time and antiedema measures for blebs to heal and skin to become normal.

X. CLINICAL CASE

Fig. 22: Bimalleolar Fracture Pre And Post Surgery

Fig. 23: Exposed Implant Following Infection

REFERENCES

- [1.] Risk Factors for Deep Surgical Site Infection Following Operative Treatment of Ankle Fractures :Ovaska, Mikko T. MD1; Mäkinen, Tatu J. MD, PhD1; Madanat, Rami MD, PhD1; Huotari, Kaisa MD, PhD2; Vahlberg, Tero MSc3;Hirvensalo, Eero MD, PhD1; Lindahl, Jan MD :The Journal of Bone & Joint Surgery: February 20, 2013 - Volume 95 - Issue 4 - p 348-35
- [2.] Predictors of poor outcomes following deep infection after internal fixation of ankle fractures Author link panelMikko T.OvaskaTatu J.MäkinenRamiMadanatTeroVahlbergaEeroHirvensaloJanLindahl,Department of Orthopaedics and Traumatology, Helsinki University Central Hospital, Topeliuksenkatu 5, 00260 Helsinki, Finland
- [3.] The timing of ankle fracture surgery and the effect on infectious complications; A case series and systematic review of the literatureTim Schepers, Mark R. De Vries, Esther M. M. Van Lieshout & Maarten Van der Elst International Orthopaedics volume 37, pages489–494(2013)
- [4.] Incidence and risk factors for surgical site infection after open reduction and internal fixation of ankle fracture A retrospective multicenter study ,Yaning Sun, MD, Huijuan Wang, MD, [...], and engqi Zhang, MD 5)
- [5.] Infection Following Operative Treatment of Ankle Fractures ,Charalampos G. Zalavras MD, Thomas Christensen MD, Nikolaos Rigopoulos MD, Paul Holtom MD & Michael J. Patzakis MD Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research® volume 467, pages1715–1720(2009)

- [6.] The impact of lifestyle risk factors on the rate of infection after surgery for a fracture of the ankle L. L. Olsen, A. M. Møller, S. Brorson, R. B. Hasselager, R. Sort Bachoura A , Guitton TG , Smith RM , Vrahas MS , Zurakowski D , Ring D .
- [7.] Infirmary and injury complexity are risk factors for surgical-site infection after operative fracture care. *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 2011; 469: 2621-30. Bach AD , Leffler M , Kneser U , Kopp J , Horch RE .
- [8.] The versatility of the distally based peroneus brevis muscle flap in reconstructive surgery of the foot and lower leg. *Ann Plast Surg* 2007; 58: 397-404. Benacquista T , Kasabian AK , Karp NS .
- [9.] The fate of lower extremities with failed free flaps. *Plast Reconstr Surg* 1996; 98: 834-40. Bibbo C , Lin SS , Beam HA , Behrens FF .
- [10.] Complications of ankle fractures in diabetic patients. *Orthop Clin North Am* 2001; 32: 113-33. [Google Scholar] Birke-Sorensen H , Malmsjo M , Rome P , et al . ; International Expert Panel on Negative Pressure Wound Therapy [NPWT-EP], Martin R, Smith J. Evidence-based recommendations for negative pressure wound therapy: treatment variables (pressure levels, wound filler and contact layer)--steps towards an international consensus. *J Plast Reconstr Aesthet Surg* 2011; 64: S1-16.
- [11.] Versatility of the sural fasciocutaneous flap in the coverage of lower third leg and hind foot defects. *J Plast Reconstr Aesthet Surg* 2006; 59: 839-45. [Google Scholar] Argenta LC , Morykwas MJ , Marks MW , DeFranzo AJ , Molnar JA , David LR .
- [12.] Vacuum-assisted closure: state of clinic art. *Plast Reconstr Surg* 2006; 117 Suppl 7: S127-42. [Google Scholar] Asloum Y , Bedin B , Roger T , Charissoux JL , Arnaud JP , Mabit C .
- [13.] Internal fixation of the fibula in ankle fractures. A prospective, randomized and comparative study: plating versus nailing. *Orthop Traumatol Surg Res* 2014; 100 Suppl 4: S255- Bach AD , Leffler M , Kneser U , Kopp J , Horch RE .
- [14.] The versatility of the distally based peroneus brevis muscle flap in reconstructive surgery of the foot and lower leg. *Ann Plast Surg* 2007; 58: 397-404. [Google Scholar] Bachoura A , Guitton TG , Smith RM , Vrahas MS , Zurakowski D , Ring D .
- [15.] Infirmary and injury complexity are risk factors for surgical-site infection after operative fracture care. *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 2011; 469: 2621-30. [Google Scholar] Bariteau JT , Fantry A , Blankenhorn B., Lareau C , Paller D , Digiovanni CW .
- [16.] A biomechanical evaluation of locked plating for distal fibula fractures in an osteoporotic sawbone model. *Foot Ankle Surg* 2014; 20: 44-7. [Google Scholar] Bauer M , Johnell O , Redlund-Johnell I , Johnsson K . Ankle fractures. *Foot Ankle* 1987; 8: 23-5. [Google Scholar]
- [17.] Thirty-year follow-up of ankle fractures. *Acta Orthop Scand* 1985; 56: 103-6. [Taylor & Francis Online], [Google Scholar] van den Bekerom MP .
- [18.] Biomechanical and clinical evaluation of posterior malleolar fractures. A systematic review of the literature. *J Trauma* 2009; 66: 279-84. [Google Scholar] van den Bekerom MP , Mutsaerts EL , van Dijk CN .
- [19.] Evaluation of the integrity of the deltoid ligament in supination external rotation ankle fractures: a systematic review of the literature. *Arch Orthop Trauma Surg* 2009; 129: 227-35. [Google Scholar] van den Bekerom MP , Lamme B , Hogervorst M , Bolhuis HW .
- [20.] Which ankle fractures require syndesmotom stabilization? *J Foot Ankle Surg* 2007; 46: 456-63. [Google Scholar] Beris AE , Kabbani KT , Xenakis TA , Mitsionis G , Soucacos PK , Soucacos PN .
- [21.] Surgical treatment of malleolar fractures. A review of 144 patients. *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 1997; 341: 90-8. [Google Scholar] Benacquista T , Kasabian AK , Karp NS .